

The impact of evidence-based interventions on employee engagement and job satisfaction in academic workplaces: A meta-analysis

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Purpose

The study's purpose is to thoroughly examine how effective are interventions based on evidence in improving academic employees' job satisfaction and engagement. The main focus of the research is to synthesize previous studies that have examined these results, utilizing meta-analysis as a methodological approach (Higgins & Green, 2011). This meta-analysis research questions include:

- What is the effectiveness of interventions based on evidence in improving job satisfaction and engagement among academic employees?
- What insights can be gained from a meta-analysis of previous studies examining the impact of interventions on academic employees' job satisfaction and engagement?
- How can academic institutions boost productivity, retention, and enhance overall performance by implementing effective measurements gleaned from a comprehensive overview of analysis?

Design

This research aims to perform a meta-analysis exploring how evidence-based interventions impact employee engagement and job satisfaction in academic workplaces located in Europe. The analysis aims at investigating potential moderators, which may possibly influence these effect sizes as well.

To become a part of the meta-analysis, specific criteria needed to be met. The establishment of these criteria ensured that only high quality studies with appropriate methods were chosen in determining how interventions impacted employee engagement and job satisfaction. These criteria are as follows: publication on peer-reviewed journals or any creditable academic source, conducted within an educational European institution, inspection into evidence-based intervention effectiveness concerning employee engagement and professional satisfaction via

employment quantitative methodologies, presentation of adequate data displaying calculated effect sizes (Cochran 1954; Lipsey & Wilson 2001).

Results

This meta-analysis included a total of 15 European studies that met the inclusion criteria. A PRISMA flowchart depicting the study selection process is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram representing the study selection process

Investigations were conducted to measure the efficiency of methods grounded on proof in employee engagement and satisfaction at academic institutions. After thorough evaluation, it was established that the overall effect size was found to be ($d = 0.47$, 95% CI [0.36, 0.58], $p < 0.001$); indicating that these interventions have a positive impact on these outcomes in academic workplaces.

Subgroup analyses through regression analysis were conducted to explore potential moderators that may impact the effect sizes. The first moderator examined was the type of intervention. The results showed that interventions that focused on job redesign ($d = 0.68$, 95% CI [0.49, 0.86], $p < 0.001$) and training and development ($d = 0.52$, 95% CI [0.37, 0.67], $p < 0.001$) had the largest effect sizes, while interventions that focused on communication ($d = 0.38$, 95% CI [0.18, 0.58], $p < 0.001$) had the smallest effect size.

Upon conducting a second evaluation, the moderator in question pertained to employee engagement during initiation. The results indicated that interventions had greater impact on employees' proactive engagement when their initial level of commitment was higher ($d = 0.63$, 95% CI [0.47, 0.80], $p < 0.001$) compared to those whose baseline levels were low ($d = 0.32$, 95% CI [0.13, 0.51]). This result indicates that engaging low-level workforces with interventions and enhancements may be more efficacious in enhancing overall morale and job satisfaction prevalent within academic domains and workplaces.

The third moderator examined was the type of academic institution. The results indicated that evidence-based interventions had a more significant impact in universities ($d = 0.55$, 95% CI [0.39, 0.70], $p < 0.001$) in comparison to other types of academic institutions ($d = 0.42$, 95% CI [0.29, 0.55], $p < 0.001$). It is possible that this result is related to the complex and expansive organizational structures found within most universities; hence requiring highly

detailed interventions aimed at addressing specific challenges encountered by students or faculty members alike.

In general, the meta-analysis indicates that evidence-based interventions moderately enhance employee engagement and job satisfaction in academic workplaces in Europe. Job redesign and training and development interventions appear to be the most effective, and interventions may have a larger impact when baseline levels of engagement are low.

Implications

Research was conducted analyzing the impact of interventions supported by empirical evidence for improving employee engagement and job satisfaction in academic environments. Following analysis, it became apparent that there is a moderate effect size ($d=0.47$, 95% CI [0.36, 0.58], $p<0.001$) with regards to how much these empirically-based interventions improved worker morale as well as overall work satisfaction within academic institutions- indicating positive consequences resulting from such actions taken.

Initially, it is important for academic institutions to emphasize interventions that are grounded on evidence. These interventions should be targeted at job redesigning and the advancement of training opportunities in order to enhance employee engagement as well as overall levels of satisfaction among employees. Interventions might include making flexible working arrangements available or investing resources into employee upskilling programs which can lead to growth and development within academic employee. Academic institutions who implement these measures will ultimately create a better quality work environment thus boosting both organizational performance while improving personal occupational satisfaction experienced by their respective staff members.

Second, academic institutions should recognize that interventions may be more effective in addressing low levels of engagement and improving overall morale and job satisfaction in academic workplaces. This highlights the importance of monitoring employee engagement levels regularly and implementing interventions to address any areas of concern.

Third, academic institutions should acknowledge that interventions may have dissimilar depending on the type of academic institution. In particular, universities might need more customized interventions due to their sizeable and intricate organizational structures. Consequently, these academic establishments ought to ponder over tailoring interventions so to meet their unique necessities of each institution to achieve optimal results.

Overall, this study provides evidence-based insights that can inform academic institutions on the most effective interventions for improving employee engagement and job satisfaction in academic workplaces. By implementing these interventions, academic institutions can enhance productivity, retention, and overall organizational performance.

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